

Outcomes of the Water-ForCE Workshop on Citizen Science for validation of water related satellite products

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History of Changes

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15.11.2022	V.0	First Draft for feedback from WP4 members
24.11.2022	V.1	Version Revised by WP4 members. QUestionnaire answers updated
25.11.2022	V.2	Last version revised by authors

List of Acronyms

CAL/VAL	Calibration and/or Validation
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EO	Earth Observation
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
QA/QC	Quality Assurance / Quality Control
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
WP	Working Package

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1 Scope

1.1 H2020 Water-ForCE

Water-ForCE is a H2020 Coordination and Support Action focused on analyzing the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and bottlenecks of the current provision of water-related services in the Copernicus Earth Observation (EO) programme. The project will result (by the end of 2023) in a roadmap document based on wide community consultation and expert knowledge and opinion.

1.2 Workshop on Citizen Science

Part of the Working Package 4 (WP4) **Aligning in situ and satellite Earth Observation activities** there is the **Task 4.4 - Integration of alternative data sources** which aims to identify possible integration between satellite remote sensing data streams and *in situ* data networks to complement or validate EO-based products. In a document from European Environment Agency's (EEA) cross-cutting coordination of the Copernicus programme's in-situ data activities - Observational data entitled "Hydrological in situ data requirements and availability", it was highlighted that Citizen Science has the potential to support CAL/VAL of satellite EO water quality products (Fry et al. 2019). This was also supported in a recent report from the EEA entitled "Lake Water Quality In-Situ Data Requirements and Availability" (Carvalho et al., 2021). To understand how **Citizen Science could be used for the validation of satellite products for water**, a group of experts was invited to answer a pre-workshop survey and they were also invited to take part in an on-line workshop entitled "**Citizen Science for the CAL/VAL of satellite aquatic products**" held on October 11th, 2022 (13:00 - 15:30 CEST) to discuss the following topics:

- Citizen Science Initiatives
- Citizen Science Challenges
- Citizen Science data harmonization, storing and sharing

In this workshop we had a total number of 63 people registered and a final number of 43 participants. The same survey will be open to all registered participants and the final results will be presented in the Deliverable 4.4 - Report on recommendations for the uptake of alternative monitoring methods.

1.3 Structure of this report

This report includes the results of the pre-workshop survey for selected experts on citizen science as well as all recommendations collected during the workshop from invited speakers and breakout discussion groups. All statements relevant to the discussion themes were kept for reference and their inclusion here does not imply community consensus. These recommendations were grouped by their relevance to common themes:

- Data gaps
- Data management
- Resourcing/Funding
- Coordination

This overview will be input to further drafting of the Roadmap, which will again be open to community feedback. In the meantime, we welcome any comments on this overview from the workshop on Citizen Science through the project and respective WP leads.

2 Results from the survey with selected experts (pre-workshop) - 13 respondents

The first question on the survey was: **“What is your expertise in Citizen Science?”**. This question was proposed to make sure that we have experts on different areas of citizen science like: Citizen Science data producer, Citizen Science data

manager, Citizen Science data user or just interested in the use of Citizen Science for Earth Observation Validation activities. The results of this first question (Figure 1) showed that there was a good representation of all groups in the respondents; however the citizen science data producers were the main contributors.

Figure 1.- Responses from question 1: “What is your expertise in Citizen Science?”

For the second question, we asked “**What is the optimal strategy to fund citizen science programs/projects?**”. In this question our goal was to figure out who should be responsible for funding Citizen Science projects and the results (Figure 2) pointed out that most of the experts believe that Local, Regional and National programs should be responsible for funding these initiatives.

Figure 2.- Responses from question 2: “What is the optimal strategy to fund Citizen Science programs/projects??”

The third question was an open end question where experts replied to the following question: “**What are the main challenges to fund Citizen Science programs/projects?**”. Answers to this question were grouped and a word cloud (Figure 3) was created to highlight the most common terms within the answers. Most of the common terms were related to the question such as “funding”, “citizen science”, “sustainability of projects” and “long term programs”. Overall, most of the challenges mentioned by the experts were related to funding opportunities (6 answers), the long-term commitment of Citizen Science projects/programs (4 answers) and reaching stakeholders and scientists to avoid the skepticism about the quality of the data collected in these initiatives (1 answer).

Figure 4.- Responses from question41: “How to best manage Citizen Science data to make them FAIR?”

Similarly to the third question, the fifth question was also an open end question where experts replied to the following question: “**What are the main challenges to make Citizen Science data FAIR?**”. Answers to this question were grouped and a word cloud (Figure 5) was created to highlight the most common terms within the answers. Most of the terms in the word cloud points to the word “lack” which was usually complemented with “lack of standards”, “lack of centralized dataset”, “lack of curated data”. Overall, most of the challenges mentioned by the experts were related to lack of a centralized, structured and curated database (3 answers), lack of common data and metadata standards (3 answers), and lack of harmonization among citizen science generated data (3 answers)..

Figure 6.- Responses from question 6: “How to make Citizen Science data reliable?”

The seventh question was also an open end question where experts replied to the following question: “**What are the main challenges to make Citizen Science data reliable?**”. Answers to this question were grouped and a word cloud (Figure 7) was created to highlight the most common terms. Excluding the main words “citizen”, “science” and “data”, we observed the common use of the words “quality”, “training”, “standard” and “funding”. Overall, most of the challenges mentioned by the experts were related to lack of proper training of the citizens (4 answers), lack of quality control and standardization (4 answers), and continuous funding to develop the infrastructure needed for the initiative (2 answers). One highlight was an answer about the lack of science communication skills, therefore, scientists should also prepare themselves to talk to the citizens.

overcome some of them. The recommendations from her presentation were summarized on Table 1.

Table 1 - Main recommendations from the presentation by Deborah V. Chapman

Themes	Recommendations
Data Gaps	Call for global collaboration to promote the generation and use of Citizen Science data for SDG indicator 6.3.2
Data Management	
Resources/Funding	Produce a policy brief to encourage governments to consider use of Citizen Science data Foster and promote Citizen Science
Coordination	Highlight best practice Case studies and successful examples

3.2 From the presentation by Janet Anstee

Janet Anstee in her talk - entitled **“Eye On Water - Australia Part of a national approach for water quality assessment”** - presented her work and experiences with Eye On Water - Australia as part of a national approach for water quality assessment. She explained how this program was used to create a network of citizen scientists to increase the data availability in data scarce areas, increase the scientific knowledge and use the data to calibrate satellite images. The recommendations from her presentation were summarized on Table 2.

Table 2 - Main recommendations from the presentation by Janet Anstee

Themes	Recommendations
Data Gaps	Engagement of citizen scientists with dedicated campaigns directed to different audiences thus increasing spatial and temporal coverage.
Data Management	Enhance quality control through videos and quizzes related to the App.
Resources/Funding	Add Citizen Science in National Operational Water programs.
Coordination	Coordinate with local communities, especially with schools.

3.3 From the presentation by Leif Olmanson

Leif Olmanson gave a talk entitled “**Using Citizen Volunteer Lake Water Quality data to Calibrate and Validate Satellite Imagery for Assessment of 10,000+ Minnesota Lakes**” highlighting the importance of a long-term state funded Citizen Science program for the validation of satellite derived products of water quality. In his talk Leif also presented how different stakeholders and citizens have passion for their lakes. The recommendations from his presentation were summarized on Table 3.

Table 3 - Main recommendations from the presentation by Leif Olmanson

Themes	Recommendations
Data Gaps	Citizen Science data need to match up with satellite passages.
Data Management	Open access to the data - especially for the ones collecting them.

Resources/Funding	Long-term Citizen Science data funded by government and local associations.
Coordination	Need to coordinate with existing local lake associations. A Water Governance program involving several actors (government, stakeholders, scientists, citizens) is important for the success of a Citizen Science Program.

3.4 From the breakout groups

During the workshop the attendees were split into different breakout rooms and were asked to discuss the following topics:

- What are the main challenges for data curation/ data sharing?
- What are the main challenges to fund Citizen Science programs/projects?
- What are the main challenges to make Citizen Science data FAIR?
- What are the main challenges to make Citizen Science data reliable?

The main recommendations from the breakout discussion are summarized on Table 4.

Table 4 - Main recommendations from the discussion in the breakout rooms

Themes	Recommendations
Data Gaps	Need to collect more biological data (i.e. plankton identification, phytoplankton pigments, biodiversity) Need more open access data.
Data Management	Data curation could be done by the national water agency. Need to provide uncertainties. Need to create data QA/QC levels.

	Standardize individual methods. Create a quality control seal to be given to curated databases.
Resources/Funding	Look for private funding sources Reinforce the need to include monitoring in funding lines. Provide long-term funding for citizen science initiatives.
Coordination	Give outstanding examples. Raising awareness on citizen science initiatives (science communication). Engage the local community to help to protect their close-by aquatic system.

4 Final Considerations

The workshop highlighted many benefits of using Citizen Science for monitoring aquatic environments such as:

- Cost-effectiveness of data acquisition and data analysis
- High spatial and temporal coverage
- Public engagement to protect their environment
- Can be used to validate with EO products if Citizen Science data is quality controlled (see Leif Olmanson's talk).

However, many challenges still need to be solved for a better use of Citizen Science programs for operational monitoring and validation of EO products. These challenges include:

- Lack of long-term funding. Not enough involvement from National/Regional Agencies.

- Lack of data quality control in most of the Citizen Science schemes affecting their reliability
- Lack of sufficient training to avoid data acquisition bias
- Lack of a standardization of data
- Lack of organization to keep citizens interested in crowdsourcing projects

5 References

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